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PHRASAL VERBS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND TRANSLATOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THEM

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Annotation:The article deals with the study of usage of phrasal verbs,their translational problems in Uzbek and in English.And,also some actual phrasal verbs are touched upon.

Key word:Phrasal verbs: go, get, come,give ,transitive, intransitive, separable, non-separable, language.

INTRODUCTION.

What is the phrasal verb?

A phrasal verb is a verb formed from two (or sometimes three) parts:a verb and an adverb or preposition.These adverbs and prepositions are called particles when they are used in phrasal verb.[7]

Most phrasal verbs are formed from a small number of verbs (for example:get,go,come,put and set)and small number of particles(for example :away,back,out,off,on,in, and up).[7]

Phrasal verbs sometimes have meaning that you can easily guess. If you know the

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meaning of each word (for example: go back, turn round, put down).

You will have to turn round here and go back.

Jeremy stopped and put down both the suitcases. [1]

Moreover, in most cases their meanings are different from the meaning of the verb they are formed from. For instance: hold up, give up, catch on and etc.

I have given up smoking (=stopped)

The idea has caught on the big way (=become popular) [4]

There are four types of phrasal verbs:

1. Transitive Phrasal Verbs;

These are verbs which must have an object. The object can come in one of two positions;

1. Between the verbs and particle(s).

I think I will put my jacket on. (Menimcha, kurtkamni kiyib olaman.)

OR

2. After the particle

I think, I will put on my jacket. 1

2. Intransitive Phrasal verbs;

The phrasal verbs which do not need an object;

You have to be the best, so you ought to go on. (Siz eng yaxshi bo'lishingiz kerak, shuning uchun siz shu tarzda davom ettirishingiz kerak.) [4]

3. Separable Phrasal verbs;

The phrasal verbs whose words can be separated to be used at different place in sentences. [3]

1. Johnny crawled under Great-Grandparent's bed. He pulled up the pillow(

2022

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OR pulled the pillow up) on his favorite chair.

He looked through Great-Grandfather's pillowcase and sheets and blankets to see if the ring had fallen off his finger while he slept.[2]

4. Non-separable Phrasal Verbs;

These are the phrasal verbs whose words cannot be separated for using them at different places in sentences. Its verb and preposition cannot be separated. They generally remain together.[1]

Whenever he could, he sought out a new road to travel (NOT he sought a new road out to travel). He had never been to that ruined church before, in spite of having traveled through those parts many times.[2]

Common English phrasal verbs with "COME"

"But finally the merchant appeared, and asked the boy to shear four sheep. He paid for the wool and asked the shepherd to come back the following year".[2].

1. Come back-return-Qaytmoq
2. Come along-accompany someone when going somewhere-(Rivojlanmoq)
3. Come off-when something becomes separated or unstuck from another thing-(Ajratoq)
4. Come out-appear or leave inside a place-(Paydobo'lmoq)
5. Come over-come to someone's house-(Ko'chibkelmoq).
6. Come on-encourage someone to do something-(Ruhlantirmoq)
7. Come up with-create or invent something-(Kashfqilmoq.)
8. Come up-appear-(Paydobo'lmoq.)
9. Come through-produce or deliver the result-(Muvaffaqiyatgaerishish)
10. Come across-to find something by accident-(Tasodifantopmoq)

2022

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“GET”

“ When I got up in the morning I tried not to look at the painting,instead studying in contents of the cellar in the dim light that fell through the window of the storage room above me”[5]

- 1.Get on with someone-have a good relationship-(Yaxshialoqadabo'lmoq)
- 2.Get at somebody-critisise someone repeatidly-(Haqoratqilmoq)
- 3.Get somebody through-successfully explained something-(Ko'ngilsizishnimuvaffaqiyatlibajarmoq)
- 4.Get on-start or continiou doing something-(Birornarsaqilishniboshlamoq)
- 5.Get somebody down-to make somebody feel sad-(Xafaqilmoq)
- 6.Get ahead-to be success-(Muvaffaqiyatgaerishmoq)
- 7.Get into-to become interested in something-(Birornarsagaqiziqmoq)
- 8.Get off-to leave a place-(Tarketmoq)
- 9.Get back-to return aplace-(qaytmoq)
- 10.Get up-to stand up-(O'rnidanturmoq)

“GIVE”

“Because you are trying to realize your destiny.And you are at the point where you are about to give it all up”[2]

- 1.Give up- to stop-(To'xtatmoq)
- 2.Give something away-(Beribyuboroq)
- 3.Give in-to finally agree to what someone wants-(Rozibo'lmoq)
- 4.Give over-to stop doing something-(Birornarsaqilishnito'xtatmoq)
- 5.Give something of-to produce heat,light,smell or a gas-(Ishlabchiqarmoq)
- 6.Give on something-to open in the direction of something.

2022

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Phrasal verbs are vital, because they are extremely common in informal English language and unless you are familiar with their meanings, understanding on formal language will be difficult. In conclusion, learning to use phrasal verbs correctly will help you sound natural in casual conversations.

REFERENCES;

1. John Eastwood "Oxford guide to English grammar" (Pages: 453, Published: 1994)
2. Paulo Coelho "The Alchemist" (Pages: 94, Published: 1992).
3. Rawdon Wyatt "Phrasal verbs and idioms"
4. Sue Kay & Vaughan Jones "Inside out" (Pages: 160, Published: 2001).
5. Tracy Chevalier "Girl with a pearl earring" (Pages: 248, Published: 1999).
6. @ablack.come (24.09.2022, 14:00)
7. @STUDYANDEXAM.come (24.09.2022, 14:00)

